

NOTES

TABLE 1—EVALUATION OF STOICHIOMETRY, CONDITIONAL STABILITY CONSTANT (K_f) AND FREE ENERGY ($\Delta^\circ G$ IN kcal mol⁻¹ AT 25^o) OF Sc^{III}-, Y^{III}- AND La^{III}- VIOLURATE COMPLEXES

Method	Ratio	Sc ^{III} -violurate		Y ^{III} -violurate		La ^{III} -violurate	
		K_f	$\Delta^\circ G$	K_f	$\Delta^\circ G$	K_f	$\Delta^\circ G$
M.R.	1 : 1						
	1 : 2	0.21 × 10 ¹³	16.927	0.095 × 10 ⁷	8.203	13.636 × 10 ¹¹	16.653
	1 : 3	4.97 × 10 ¹⁰	25.658	0.53 × 10 ¹⁷	22.952	1.56 × 10 ¹⁵	20.85
	1 : 4	0.292 × 10 ²⁰	26.713	11.53 × 10 ²⁰	28.904	0.252 × 10 ¹⁷	22.404
C.V.	2 : 1	0.148 × 10 ⁶	7.095				
	1 : 1	0.803 × 10 ⁸	10.276	0.03 × 10 ⁹	8.888	0.45 × 10 ⁹	10.503
	1 : 2	1.254 × 10 ¹³	16.602	0.155 × 10 ¹²	15.357	9.932 × 10 ¹³	17.836
	1 : 4	0.345 × 10 ²⁰	268.19	3.56 × 10 ²⁰	28.204	2.141 × 10 ²³	30.645
S.L.	1 : 1	2.63 × 10 ¹⁰	14.30	19.395 × 10 ¹²	18.225	0.12 × 10 ⁸	9.715
	1 : 2	1.022 × 10 ¹⁶	21.97			10.74 × 10 ¹⁷	24.745
L.L.	1 : 1	0.049 × 10 ⁷	7.809	0.02 × 10 ⁴	3.158	0.018 × 10 ⁴	3.095
pH	1 : 1	0.267 × 10 ⁹	10.192	0.138 × 10 ⁶	7.054	0.135 × 10 ⁷	8.413

Stoichiometry of the complexes : The composition of Sc^{III}, Y^{III} and La^{III} complexes was determined from conductometric titrations, conductometric measurements and spectrophotometric methods (molar ratio, M.R.¹⁵; continuous variation, C.V.^{14,15}; straight line, S.L.¹⁶; and limiting logararithmic, L.L.¹⁸ methods). The results obtained are recorded in Table 1.

The conditional formation constant : The conditional stability constants of the complexes were evaluated making use of the results of the spectrophotometric methods¹³⁻¹⁶ and the analytical (A-pH) method¹⁹. The free energy change ($\Delta^\circ G$) of the complexes was calculated using the relation

$$\Delta^\circ G = -RT \ln k.$$

The results of stoichiometry, stability constant and free energy of the complexes are presented in Table 1. The data indicate that the stability of the complexes are in the order La^{III}->Y^{III}->Sc^{III}-violurates.

The complexation takes place through covalent linkage between the central metal ion and the C-OH group, and coordination between the central metal ion and the nitroso group²⁰. Complexation through covalent linkage is confirmed from the results of the conductivity experiments. The results show an increase in conductance values with the increase of [VA] as a result of increasing conducting power of the solutions containing ionic species (H⁺ ions) liberated due to dissociation of the ligand which manifests the gradual increase of the molar conductivity of the solution. The mobility of the hydrogen ions liberated, moves faster and gather enhanced electrical field and thus increases the conductivity of the solution. Linkage between violuric acid and the metal ions in the complexes (1 : 1) can be typified as follows :

References

1. P. P. SOLODOVNIKOV, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1963, 18, 1026.
2. M. ZIEGLER and O. CLEMSER, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 1956, 1515.
3. M. ZIEGLER, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1958, 164, 387.
4. R. M. AWADALLAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 685.
5. I. M. ISSA, R. M. ISSA, A. M. HAMMAM and K. A. IDRIS, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1974, 17, 911
6. A. I. CHERKESOV and N. M. ALYKOV, *Zh. Anal. Khim.*, 1965, 20, 202.
7. H. T. BESCHETNOVA, *Sb. Nauch. Soobshch. Eagastan. Zh. Khim.*, 1972, 15022.
8. N. H. FERMAN, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 6th ed., Van Nostrand, New York, 1966.
9. J. ROSIN, "Reagent Chemicals and Standards", 5th ed., Van Nostrand, New York, 1967.
10. H. T. S. BRITTON, "Hydrogen Ions", 4th ed., Van Nostrand, New York, Vol. 1, 1956.
11. R. M. ISSA, M. S. MASSOUD and S. E. ZAYAN, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1969, 12, 309.
12. E. M. KHAIRY, A. E. MAHGOUB and I. M. KENAWI, *Egypt. J. Chem.*, 1974, 17, 811.
13. J. H. YOE and M. M. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, 16, 111.
14. P. JOB and C. R. HEBD, *Seances Acad. Sci.*, 1925, 180, 928.
15. F. G. SCHERIEF and A. M. AWAD, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, 24, 149.
16. E. I. ASMUS, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1960, 178, 104.
17. A. E. HARVEY and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4488.
18. H. E. BENT and C. L. FRENCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 568.
19. R. M. AWADALLAH, M.Sc. Thesis, Assiut University, 1971.
20. R. M. AWADALLAH, *Aust. J. Chem.*, submitted for publication.

Spectral Studies on Bis-(β -Naphthylidene-*o*-amino phenolato) Chelates of Cerium(III), Samarium(III), Gadolinium(III), Dysprosium(III), Cobalt(II) and Chromium(III)

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Ce^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III}, Co^{II} and Cr^{III} complexes of tridentate Schiff base derived from the condensation of *o*-aminophenol and β -naphthylglyoxal have been prepared and studied by

TABLE 1—COLOUR, M.p., STABILITY CONSTANT AND ANALYTICAL DATAS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			K	ΔF kcal mol ⁻¹
			C	H	N		
[Ce(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]Cl	Light brown	200	59.59 (59.00)	3.58 (3.47)	3.86 (3.80)	1.285 × 10 ¹¹ (19.28)	-15.476
[Dy(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]NO ₃	Brown	215	55.98 (55.50)	3.10 (3.00)	5.44 (5.40)	1.568 × 10 ¹¹ (20.86)	-15.622
[Gd(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]NO ₃	Dark brown	205	56.32 (56.20)	3.13 (3.07)	5.48 (5.35)	2.007 × 10 ¹¹ (20.40)	-17.169
[Sm(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]NO ₃	Dark brown	217	56.84 (56.70)	3.16 (3.06)	5.53 (5.38)	6.621 × 10 ¹⁰ (19.66)	-15.095
[Cr(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]Cl	Brown	220	68.03 (67.90)	3.78 (3.59)	4.41 (4.48)	2.717 × 10 ¹¹ (8.22)	-15.958
[Co(C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ N) ₂]	Brown	230	71.29 (71.04)	3.96 (3.80)	4.62 (4.85)	1.783 × 10 ¹¹ (9.62)	-15.720

absorption and infrared spectroscopy. The stoichiometry of the complexes is established by spectrophotometric methods and elemental analysis. The bindings of the functional groups of the ligand to metal on complexation have been confirmed by infrared spectral study.

Experimental

The ligand β -naphthylidene-*o*-aninophenol was prepared by refluxing the equimolar quantities of both glyoxal and amine in ethanolic medium in presence of a few drops of acetic acid. The content were refluxed for 2 h and then poured into distilled water and the solid filtered off. Finally it was washed with ethanol.

The complexes were prepared by refluxing the metal salt and ligand solution in dimethylformamide in the ratio 1 : 2 for 2 h, and then kept for 2 or 3 days to concentrate the volume. The crystals of the complexes were recovered and washed.

The composition of the complexes was ascertained by the elemental analysis. The infrared spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The optical density was measured on Bauch and Lomb Spectronic 20.

The colour and melting point of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Vosburgh and Cooper's method was applied to determine the number of complexes formed by the interaction of ligand and metal in the system. Equimolar solutions of metal and ligand of different sets were prepared in the ratio 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 1 : 3 and 1 : 4. In the plot between optical density vs wavelength the maxima of curves showed the number of the complexes formed in the system. The wavelength at which the maxima occurred was suitable for further study and for each system this method was applied. Molar ratio method was applied to determine the composition of the complexes. The curves

were plotted between optical density and volume of variant, and break in the curves shows the stoichiometry of all the complexes.

Stability constant K_s was evaluated by molar ratio method by the formula $K_s = (1-\alpha)/4\alpha^2 C^2$, where α is the degree of dissociation and C is the total concentration of the complex in mol dm⁻³.

Free energy, ΔF of complex formation has been evaluated by the equation, $\Delta F = -2.303 RT \log K_s$. Stability constant and free energy of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Ir spectral studies: The point of attachment of the ligand with the metal ion has been confirmed by studying the infrared spectra of the ligand and the isolated chelates.

The strong band appearing at 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O) in the ligand is shifted to lower frequency 1680-1690 cm⁻¹ on complexation in all the systems, suggesting the formation of C-O-M bonding. The strong band at 1630 cm⁻¹ (CH=N) in the ligand was lowered to 1590-1610 cm⁻¹ on complexation indicating the formation of M-N bond. Hence, it is concluded that coordination occurs through CH=N and C=O groups. The peak at 3400 cm⁻¹ (OH) in the ligand vanished on complexation. Therefore, it is concluded that the third point of attachment of metal to ligand occurs through the oxygen atom of OH group of the ligand.

References

1. A. N. SUNDAR RAM and C. P. PRABHABHARAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 536.
2. OM PRAKASH, R. C. GUPTA and S. P. MUSHRAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, 18, 534.
3. P. K. SHARMA and P. ACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 961.
4. G. S. MANKU and A. N. BHAT, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, 15, 138.
5. M. MOHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1977, 15, 247.
6. B. SEN and R. DOSTEN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, 32, 2707.